

Equilibrium Study of the Mixed Complexes of Uranyl Ion with 3,5-Dinitrosalicylic as Primary and Some Substituted Carboxylic Acids as Secondary Ligands

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The stabilities of simple and mixed complexes of uranyl ion have been studied with 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid as primary and malic, chlorosuccinic, dimercapto succinic, maleic, methylmalonic, dimethylmalonic, picolinic, dipicolinic or quinolinic acid as secondary ligands by pH metric method. Uranyl forms only 1:1 complex with maleic, chlorosuccinic and dimercapto succinic acid while 1:1 and 1:2 complexes are formed with all the other ligands. The relationship between complex stability and ligand basicity has been used to discuss the formation of mixed-ligand complexes.

THERE has been continuing interest over the years on mixed-ligand complexes of metal ions with biologically important ligands¹⁻⁴. Considering the biological significance of uranyl compounds⁵⁻⁶, the ternary complexes of UO_2^{2+} -amino acids with some carboxylic acids have been studied^{7,8}. As a part of systematic study of UO_2^{2+} -complexes with amino acids, pyridine carboxylic, thiodicarboxylic and simple dicarboxylic acids having 2 and 3 coordination sites, we had earlier reported the formation of series of complexes with these ligands⁹⁻¹³. We now report the mixed-ligand complex formation, occurring when uranyl ion is mixed with 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid and other carboxylic acids. In addition, the present work was undertaken to examine the complexing ability of substituted succinic, malonic and pyridine carboxylic acids with UO_2^{2+} -3,5-dinitrosalicylic binary complexes and to discuss the preferential formation of ternary complexes over binary ones.

Experimental

The ligands such as chlorosuccinic, dimercapto-succinic, methylmalonic, dimethylmalonic, picolinic, dipicolinic and quinolinic acids were obtained from Fluka (Germany). 3,5-Dinitrosalicylic, malic, maleic acids were B.D.H., AnalaR reagents. The purity of the ligands was checked by their melting points. Uranyl nitrate (B.D.H., AnalaR) was dissolved in perchloric acid to prepare stock solution. All solutions were prepared in glass distilled water. Details for the other chemicals and measurement of pH are given in earlier papers¹¹⁻¹⁴.

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants of the simple complexes were calculated by Irving and Rossotti's method¹⁵. The mixed-

ligand stabilities and other equilibrium constants (Table 1) were evaluated by the method of Rama-moorthy and Manning¹⁷ as outlined earlier¹². The formation of simple and mixed species of uranyl complexes was the same and relevant equilibria were discussed earlier^{13,19}. To illustrate the equilibrium concentrations in the systems containing 3,5-dinitrosalicylic and dicarboxylic acids, Fig. 1 shows the percentage distribution of the complexes formed in UO_2^{2+} -3,5-dinitrosalicylic-dipicolinic acid system as a function of pH.

Fig. 1. Distribution of various species present in ternary uranyl ion-3,5-dinitrosalicylic-(H_2X)-dipicolinic (H_2Y) acid system as a function of pH. M^0 = uranyl ion free, MY = uranyl ion-3,5-dinitrosalicylic, MY_2 = uranyl ion-(3,5-dinitrosalicylic)₂, MX = uranyl ion-dipicolinic, MX_2 = uranyl ion-(dipicolinic)₂ and MXY = uranyl ion-dipicolinic-3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid. $\mu = 0.1M$ ($NaClO_4$), Temp. $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. $C_M = C_X = C_Y = 2.0 \times 10^{-2}M$.

TABLE I—LOGARITHMS OF EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS OF TERNARY COMPLEXES OF UO_2^{2+} -3,5-DINITROSALICYLIC**
(H_2Y)-SECONDARY (H_2X) LIGANDS

Secondary ligand/acids	$\mu = 0.1 M (NaClO_4)$						$\Delta \log K$
	β_{XY}	Standard deviations are given in parentheses					
		K_{DXYa}	K_{2FX}	K_{2XY}	$K_{MX_1^*}$	$K_{MX_2^*}$	
Malic	10.37(3)	0.24	3.98	4.87	5.50	3.63	-1.52
Chlorosuccinic	8.70(1)	0.39 ^b	2.31	5.13	3.57	-	-1.25
Dimercaptosuccinic	8.41(3)	1.26 ^e	1.82	5.15	3.06	-	-1.24
		0.41 ^b					
Maleic	10.15(2)	-1.24 ^c	3.76	5.00	5.15	-	-1.39
		0.26 ^b					
		-1.39 ^e					
Methylmalonic	11.53(2)	0.50	5.14	4.83	6.70	4.22	-1.56
Dimethylmalonic	11.27(2)	0.52	4.88	4.95	6.32	4.05	-1.44
Picolinic	9.69(3)	0.04	3.30	5.23	4.46	3.75	-1.16
Quinolinic	9.80(3)	0.16	3.40	5.15	4.65 [@]	3.65 [@]	-1.25
Dipicolinic	11.48(4)	0.58	5.09	6.04	5.44	5.24	-0.35

a = $MX_2 + MY_2 \rightleftharpoons 2MXY$, b = $MX + MY_2 \rightleftharpoons MXY + MY$ and c = $MX + MY \rightleftharpoons MXY + M$
 ** $\log K_{MY_1} = 6.39$ and $\log K_{MY_2} = 4.74$
 * ref. 11.
 @ ref. 10.

In the system studied, all the ligands form 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 chelates except maleic, chlorosuccinic and dimercapto succinic acids. 3,5-Dinitrosalicylic acid can be considered as primary ligand and malic, maleic, chlorosuccinic, dimercaptosuccinic, methylmalonic, dimethylmalonic, picolinic, dipicolinic and quinolinic acids, which can respectively form seven, six, seven, seven, six, six, five, five and seven membered rings around the uranyl ion, as secondary ligands $\Delta \log K$ values (Table 1) are negative for all the systems and indicate the preferential formation of ternary complexes over binary.

During the course of investigation, the order of $\Delta \log K$ was reported^{20,21} as carboxylic-carboxylic. < carboxylic - phenolic < phenolic - phenolic acid systems. In the present work, $\Delta \log K$ values are intermediate and are in agreement with earlier findings. Sigel²² reported a method for the estimation of stability constants by the relation between ligand basicity and complex stability. The plots of $\Delta \log K$ vs ΣpK gave an inverse as well as direct relationship between these two quantities for the mixed-ligand complexes of transition metal ions. These conclusions have been amply confirmed in subsequent studies involving dipeptides and amino acids in aqueous medium²³. In the systems under investigation, the plot of $\Delta \log K$ vs ΣpK (Fig. 2) gave direct relationship between these two quantities for closely related ligands. However, the point corresponding to dimethylmalonic acid as secondary ligand deviates from the straight line. The destabilized nature of the mixed-complex in this system is explained on the basis of steric hindrance due to the presence of two methyl groups and two nitro groups in dimethylmalonic acid and 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid, respectively. In view of this, the higher value of mixed-ligand stability (Table 1) for methylmalonic

than that of dimethylmalonic acid system is also understandable.

Fig. 2. Relation between $\Delta \log K$ and ligand stability for ternary complexes of UO_2^{2+} -3,5-dinitrosalicylic-carboxylic acids. Carboxylic acids: 1) maleic, 2) chlorosuccinic, 3) dimercaptosuccinic, 4) maleic, 5) methylmalonic, 6) dimethylmalonic, 7) picolinic, 8) quinolinic. $\mu = 0.1M (NaClO_4)$, $t = 30^\circ$.

K_{DXY} values in most of the systems studied here are close to those predicted on statistical considerations. The value of 0.04 of K_{DXY} in 3,5-dinitrosalicylic-picolinic acid system indicates the equal tendency of mixed-ligand formation by disproportionation reaction and dianion to bond 1 : 1 UO_2^{2+} -picolinate complex. The values -1.39 and +0.26, corresponding to maleic, chlorosuccinic and dimercapto succinic acids as secondary ligands indicate the stabilized nature of 1 : 1 UO_2^{2+} -3,5-dinitrosalicylate and ternary complex, respectively.

The formation of ternary complex is mainly dependent on ring size of the chelate which seems to offset the increasing basicity of the secondary ligands observed from the direct relationship between K_{2YX} and the product of the acid dissociation constants for the closely related ligands. The inverse relationship between these two quantities is also reported in our studies on mixed-ligand complexes of uranyl ion involving pyridine carboxylic and dicarboxylic acids as ligands^{11,24}.

The values of K_{2YX} and K_{MX_2} (Table 1) indicate the formation of mixed complexes over the simple except for the systems involving maleic, chlorosuccinic and dimercaptosuccinic acids as secondary ligands. A comparison of K_{2XY} and K_{MY_2} , especially in the systems involving methylmalonic, dimethylmalonic and dipicolinic acid as secondary ligands reveals the preferential formation of ternary complexes over binary ones.

The order of overall stabilities is methylmalonic > dipicolinic > dimethylmalonic > malic > maleic > quinolinic > picolinic > chlorosuccinic > dimercaptosuccinic, which is in accordance with the 1:1 binary stabilities. The plots of β_{XY} vs K_{MX_1} (Fig. 3) gave direct relationship. However, the point corresponding to dipicolinic acid complex deviates from the straight line.

Fig. 3. Relation between β_{XY} and $\log K_{MX_1}$ for ternary complexes of uranyl ion with 3,5-dinitrosalicylic and carboxylic acids. Carboxylic acids: 1) malic, 2) chlorosuccinic, 3) dimercaptosuccinic, 4) maleic, 5) methylmalonic, 6) dimethylmalonic, 7) picolinic, 8) quinolinic, 9) dipicolinic. $\mu = 0.1M$ ($NaClO_4$), $t = 30^\circ$.

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